

ELECTROMAGNETIC PERFORMANCE OF MECHANICALLY LOADED COMPOSITE METAMATERIALS

B.J. Arritt

United States Air Force Research Laboratory/Space Vehicles Directorate
3550 Aberdeen Ave SE, Kirtland AFB, NM 87117

AFRL.RVSV@kirtland.af.mil

A.F. Starr

SensorMetrix, Inc.

astarr@sensormetrix.com

D.R. Smith

Duke University, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

drsmith@ee.duke.edu

SUMMARY

The field of metamaterials has seen tremendous advancements in the design, modeling, and development of structures with novel ElectroMagnetic (EM) properties. However, nothing had been done to characterize how those EM properties change when a metamaterial structure is transitioned into a relevant environment (i.e. mechanical and thermal loading). This research seeks to understand the linkage between the mechanical loading of these multi-component, inclusion-intensive structures, and their resultant changes in EM performance; thus laying the foundation for the eventual operational use of these novel multifunctional structures.

Keywords: composite, modeling, metamaterial, electromagnetic, inclusions, multifunctional

OVERVIEW

In the last several years, the nascent field of ElectroMagnetic (EM) metamaterials has received an extraordinary amount of interest [1]. Metamaterials [2] are artificially structured composite materials, made by patterning subwavelength inclusions, which can exhibit electromagnetic properties difficult or even impossible to achieve with traditional materials; one of the most widely known being negative index of refraction. The ability to design and deliver tailored electromagnetic properties (reflectivity, absorptivity, transmittance, index of refraction, wave impedance, and negative phase advance) opens a world of possibilities and conveys game-changing capabilities for a variety of applications. As depicted in figure 1, metamaterials allow access to more of the electromagnetic parameter space. Additionally, metamaterial structures are not limited to isotropic or homogenous realizations; gradient and anisotropic materials can

be engineered to expand the realm of possibilities. As a result of this vast potential, many governments and commercial entities have invested heavily in the development of metamaterials for a wide range of frequencies of interest[3].

Figure 1: Metamaterials open up a much broader design space, in terms of controlling the propagation of electromagnetic waves

While tremendous advancements have been made in our abilities to produce novel electromagnetic properties [4], little has been done to understand the material's suitability in an operational environment. In RF and microwave frequency regimes, where wavelengths are of length scales equal to or greater than centimeters, associated devices and systems tend to be correspondingly large. This naturally suggests, or in cases requires, the incorporation of electromagnetic response into structurally large systems, which in turn can place mechanical and other environmental demands on the material, particularly where the material may be inherently multifunctional. Of critical importance is an understanding of the interplay between electromagnetic and mechanical phenomena.

Metamaterials are advantageous for space applications, because their electromagnetic performance can be largely independent of the properties of the baseline material. As such, we are free to use materials that already demonstrate space-hardness (resistance to atomic oxygen, radiation, UV, low outgassing, etc.), as long as they don't seriously degrade the structure's EM performance. The simplest case is to choose materials that are transparent at the frequency range of interest, allowing the metamaterial's metallic inclusions to dominate the overall EM properties of the structure.

This ability to decouple material properties from a metamaterial's effective EM properties has resulted in a wide variety of instantiations of metamaterial structures. Some of the simpler structures are based on metallic foils adhered to a polymeric backing structure. However, some of the more advanced multi-functional/symbiotic metamaterial structures feature thousands of 3-D unit cells with metallic inclusion that run both parallel and transverse to the lamina in a complex composite. It is these structures that are particularly interesting for our group, in that they are designed to both carry load and interact with EM radiation in a very specific fashion.

However, metamaterial properties are strongly geometry dependent; both within the unit cell, and in the pattern of those unit cells (the array). As a metamaterial is mechanically loaded, the geometry at the unit cell and array levels is necessarily altered, leading to a shift in EM properties. Additionally, as the sample is loaded, a number of symmetries (both within the unit cell and array) are no longer present, leading to reduced efficiencies, and greater complexities in the modeling of the new EM properties. Yet, given the dispersive nature of metamaterials, and the variety of their intended operational environments, understanding this interdependency is critically important.

Figure 2. At left, depiction of metamaterial unit cell; typical metamaterial samples contain many thousands of cells. Central picture; hardware from Duke University's successful 2-D cloaking experiment [5]. At right, glass-fiber composite metamaterial where index of refraction is varied radially, producing a flat plate able to focus radiation at microwave frequencies.

A significant benefit of metamaterials is that the numerous, sub-wavelength inclusions result in effective medium behaviors that can equivalently be described as piecewise continuous constitutive parameters; i.e. permittivity and permeability [6]. The ability to model the EM properties of the metamaterial as a continuous medium enables coupling with similar models utilized for assessing mechanical behavior.

To better understand the linkage between mechanical loading and EM properties, the team of the US Air Force Research Laboratory/Space Vehicles Directorate, SensorMetrix, and Duke University are developing the theoretical underpinnings that bridge the physics of mechanically loaded multi-component, inclusion-intensive composite structures [7-9] to the physics of EM propagation in complex media. In parallel, the team is developing and operating unique test facilities for the purposes of validating and improving these analytical predictions. The goal of this research is to ultimately develop a continuum mechanics based analytical tool that contains both mechanical and EM response to environmental loading (mechanical as well as thermal).

Some significant technical hurdles must be overcome to achieve this goal. The first is to understand how EM response is dependent upon mechanical and thermal loading. Complicating the matter is the fact that both mechanical and EM properties can be extremely anisotropic. The second is to develop software tools capable of accommodating these traditionally disparate realms of physics with the necessary resolution. These tools are absolutely essential if metamaterials are to successfully transition into an operational system; the promise of metamaterials is fundamentally diminished if designers are forced to mechanically and thermally isolate these structures.

Investigations currently focus on structural designs for high X-Band frequencies (~10 GHz). This frequency regime is advantageous because of its utility for a number of applications, the maturity of the manufacturing processes, and the resultant availability of samples. This paper will discuss the team's initial efforts to meet the above stated goal, as well as describe the novel testbed being developed at the Air Force Laboratory/Space Vehicles Directorate.

ANALYSIS

Initial analyses were conducted to develop an understanding of how mechanical loading affects EM properties. These studies focused exclusively on normal incidence interactions and materials with resonant behavior (as opposed to broad-band behavior, as detailed in [10]). Temperature dependence was not yet assessed.

Figure 3 depicts an example of a unit cell design [11]. This particular unit cell is designed to only transmit a single polarization of incoming radiation; all other polarizations are either reflected or absorbed into the material. This class of metamaterials provides the simplest test and analysis case and forms the first building block towards understanding the complex interplay between mechanical loading and the resultant shift in EM properties.

Figure 3: Example of a unit cell for EM transmission in one polarization plane [10].

Figure 4 presents the world's first set of numerical results, tying mechanical strain to changes in effective EM properties. The graph shows the transmission (S_{21}) over the frequency range of 8.5 to 10 GHz. For the scenario depicted in figure 4, the polarization plane (i.e. the plane formed by the electric field and propagation vectors, E and k in figure 3) coincides with the direction of mechanical loading. The strain from the load induces a shift in the unit cell's self inductance and capacitance, leading to a shift in the structure's EM response [12, 13]. As shown on the graph, an increase in load results in a lower frequency response.

Also in the figure is a metamaterial sample designed specifically for this research. The models, as well as the sample, feature unit cells that are similar to that depicted in figure 3; i.e. transmission only occurs in a single plane of polarization. A number of assumptions were included in these initial models, to include: 1) linear, homogeneous, isotropic material, 2) tensile loading resulting in purely elastic behavior, 3) perfect adhesion between copper unit cells, and polymeric backing structure, and 4) Poisson's ratio of 0.48 (material property provided by the manufacturer of the elastomeric backing structure used for the sample depicted in figure 4).

While these assumptions are not valid for the majority of the structural concepts of interest, they were included to quickly generate these first order approximations. The approximations were generated to answer the team's first set of questions: 1) is there a dependency between mechanical strain and EM performance, and 2) is that dependency strong enough to merit this line of research?

As figure 4 demonstrates, there is a dependency between mechanical strain and EM characteristics in these metamaterials. Additionally, this effect is significant enough to merit further investigation, due to the unique behavior of the materials being investigated. The metamaterials in this effort provide extremely narrow-band behavior, based on the resonance of the unit cells. It is the strength and frequency of that resonance that drives the overall performance of the metamaterial structure.

Figure 4 is data from a model that contains a single unit cell. However, a metamaterial sample, with many unit cells, may have much narrower peaks due to interference with neighboring cells; the slenderness of the peak being a function of the tolerances on, and dispersion of, each of the unit cells. Due to this narrow-band behavior, a slight shift in the strength or peak frequency can have a dramatic effect on the overall performance of the metamaterial structure.

Figure 4: Simulation showing shift in S-parameters (over 8-10 GHz), due to tensile loading (sample at right). Incident radiation is polarized along plane of tensile loading; higher loading results in lower frequency response.

In order to produce the data in figure 4, a model of the unit cell was run in HFSS (a microwave modeling package). The output shows S-parameters (reflection, or S11, and transmission, or S21) as a function of operating frequency and strain level. Figure 5 shows the frequency of maximum/peak response as a function of applied strain.

Figure 5: Peak frequency as a function of applied strain

Figure 5 appears to indicate a roughly linear trend between strain and peak frequency for a scenario where load is coincident with the plane of polarization. However, low resolution in the model (both spatially and spectrally) result in significant higher order terms, and large error in the trendline. Future models that incorporate finer meshes and frequency steps should help smooth out the trend, and enable more confident appraisals of the dependency.

For scenarios where the direction of loading is orthogonal to the polarization plane, Poisson’s ratio causes a spectral shift in the opposite direction, and with less magnitude. Assuming the data in figures 4 and 5 indicates a linear trend between strain and change in peak frequency, finding the change in frequency for the orthogonal loading scenario is found via a straightforward fashion: simply multiply the change in frequency for the previous, coincident scenario (figures 4 and 5) by negative Poisson’s ratio. As an example, when the load is coincident with polarization, 10% strain produces a 140 MHz decrease in the resonant frequency. For our material, with a Poisson’s ratio of 0.48, a 10% strain applied orthogonal to the polarization will cause a 67 MHz increase in the resonant frequency.

Of greater interest is what happens to the EM properties when the loading is neither aligned with, nor orthogonal to the polarization plane. The misalignment causes a break in the fundamental symmetry of the unit cell, resulting in electric and magnetic transmission paths that are no longer purely orthogonal to each other (a requirement for EM transmission in free-space). First principles would indicate that transmission is thus halted, however, some in the field have indicated that other non-linear effects may prove dominant and allow some form of propagation. The amount of disagreement in the field, and its resultant disparity in the models, further validates the requirement for empirical data to indicate which is the appropriate model.

The next unit cell investigated is one that is axi-symmetrically isotropic; i.e. its EM performance is independent of the rotation of the plane of polarization (when in an unloaded state). Figure 6 depicts a 3-dimensional isotropic cube. Each unit cell of the cube is composed of three orthogonal planar cells that feature axi-symmetric isotropy.

Much as in the previous scenarios, when the plane of polarization is co-incident with the direction of tensile loading, the frequency response decreases with increasing load, and when the plane of polarization is orthogonal to direction of tensile loading, the frequency response increases with increasing load (although to a lesser degree, as described before).

Figure 6: 3-D Isotropic metamaterial structure [14]. As viewed from the top, each unit cell provides axi-symmetric isotropy. Principal axes are annotated drawn on the picture.

Of greater interest is when the polarization is neither coincident with, nor orthogonal to, the direction of tensile loading (applied along one of the principal axes). The simplest solution would involve dissecting the EM wave into two orthogonal polarizations (aligned with the principal axes), analyze each, and then apply superposition to achieve the final solution. However, there is currently debate regarding the validity of that solution. The concern revolves around the induced asymmetry between the principal axes and the likelihood that this asymmetry produces a number of non-linear effects, to include cross-polarization and chirality [15]. This debate further demonstrates the requirement for experimental validation. Figure 7 demonstrates a solution according to superposition.

A few observations can be made from the data presented in figure 7. The first is that as tensile loading increases, the increased asymmetry in the unit cell results in a splitting of the response. This splitting reduces the strength of the peak and spreads the spectrum.

In a similar vein, complexities and debate exist for conditions where the load is not applied along one of the principal axes. In the reference frame of the unit cell, such loading will manifest itself as a combination of a tensile and shear stresses. This shear further breaks down the symmetry of the unit cell, again resulting in increased non-linear effects.

Figure 7: Plane of polarization is 45 degrees from the principal axes; superposition solution.

TESTBED

Experimental validation of these models requires a unique test capability. The testbed used for this research must be able to apply and hold loads, determine strain levels in the material sample in an RF environment, and determine the material's EM characteristics. As mentioned previously, the system is currently set up to test hardware designed to operate at and around 10 GHz (X-Band).

The central piece of the testbed is an MTS Axial Hydraulic Loadframe. The loadframe is capable of applying up to 250 kN of tensile and compressive force and is connected to a customized control system, also developed by MTS Corporation. Strain is measured using either a laser extensometer or fiber-optics with integrated fiber-Bragg's gratings, depending on the anticipated strain levels. Strain gauges would not work for these tests, due to their sensitivity to X-Band radiation (the fiber-optics and laser extensometer are insensitive to this type of EM radiation). The extensometer is an MTS Model LX300, with 0.2-0.32" capacity. The fiber optics are connected to a Micron Optics si425 Optical Sensing Interrogator system. As a previous paper demonstrated [16], the system is capable of consistently delivering sub-microstrain resolution and the accuracy of the system's data has been independently verified against traditional strain gauges. The system is also capable of expanding to simultaneously interrogate 16 fiber-optic channels. This capability may prove indispensable when the research progresses to more complex loading scenarios and structures.

This research requires the testing of relatively large samples. In order to mitigate the influence of edge effects, the test section of each sample is a 6"x6" slab of metamaterial (as shown in figure 3). This requires the development of novel clamping mechanisms to apply a consistent strain map over the majority of the test section; mitigating the effect of alignment errors. In addition to pure tension, separate clamping mechanisms are being developed to induce shear loads on the metamaterial unit cells, as well as out-of-plane bending (depicted in figure 8).

Figure 8: Metamaterial is bent out of the plane of the applied load. Such a configuration is necessary to avoid interference with the path of the EM radiation used to characterize the structure's performance

The next piece of equipment is a HP Vector Network Analyzer, capable of operating at 1 to 40 GHz. It is connected to 2 Radio Frequency (RF) horns optimized for performance in the X-Band. Each horn is mounted onto a stand, via stepper motors that rotate the two horns in a synchronous fashion. This allows for fully automated assessments of the material's polarization-dependent behavior while under static loading conditions. The stands are currently fixed, but enable characterization of both transmission (S21) and reflection (S11) parameters. Future improvements on the system will include the capability to assess off-normal performance. It is anticipated that each horn will have a full 3 degrees of freedom (rotation of the plane of polarization and rotation about the vertical and the horizontal axes).

The final piece of equipment is a custom, portable LabView test-stand. The loadframe controller, Micron Optics system, and Vector Network Analyzer all have USB or Ethernet outputs, which can be routed into the LabView system. The system also controls the stepper motors, via an open-loop.

Additional plans include testing the structure's temperature-dependent mechanical and EM performance. Structures exposed to the extremes of space may experience temperatures ranging from -150 to +150 °C. Testing these structures though this extended temperature range will require the development of a novel environmental chamber that is compatible with RF transmission and application of mechanical loads.

TEST CONDUCT

While the team was preparing for hardware testing, the Vector Network Analyzer was pulled to support a higher priority flight program; it will not be available until late April. The unfortunate result is that no empirical data was ready in time for the production of this paper.

When this equipment does become available, the first order of business is to develop a robust calibration scheme. To perform a traditional “free-space” characterization of a metamaterial sample, the current calibration sequence can be relatively straightforward: a background signal is assessed, the sample is placed in the beam path, and the previously recorded background noise is filtered out of the readings. For these more traditional tests, the only variable that changes is the introduction of the metamaterial sample.

However, for the tests required of this research, some items will necessarily displace while data is being collected. Initial empirical studies will be conducted to understand how movement of the loadframe’s arms influence the background noise. The aim is to determine the extensibility of the calibration scheme and to answer the following questions; how much displacement can be handled before another calibration step is required, how linear is the change in background noise, and does the displacement of the loadframe arms result in the formation of standing waves or other significant sources of noise?

CONCLUSIONS

The team of the United States Air Force Research Laboratory/Space Vehicles Directorate, Duke University, and SensorMetrix is working to develop an analytical basis for assessing the connection between mechanical loading and changes in electromagnetic performance. Current debate surrounding the theoretical basis for these models clearly validates the requirement for empirical data.

This research is necessary for the eventual transition of metamaterials onto operational systems. Such systems will impart mechanical and thermal loading into the metamaterial sample, resulting in a change in effective EM properties. The interdependencies between load and EM properties must be understood in order to mitigate, or potentially exploit this phenomenon.

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References

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² Term “metamaterial” originated in DARPA-DSO program of same name. DARPA definition of metamaterials is “a class of ordered nanocomposites that exhibit exceptional properties not readily observed in nature. These properties arise from qualitatively new response functions that are: (1) not observed in the constituent materials and (2) result from the inclusion of artificially fabricated, extrinsic, low dimensional inhomogeneities”.

³John Young, Director DDR&E, in a 24 August 2007 memo, identified metamaterials as an area of strategic investment for the Dept. of Defense

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